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Translation Equivalence of Hyperbolic Expression used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 Official Webpages

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Abstract

This study aims to recognize the translation equivalence through the translation methods of hyperbolic expressions used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 official webpages. The data used in this study is the hyperbolic expressions gained from the official webpages of iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro and iPhone SE 2022. The research stages applied in this study are analyzing the data based on the qualitative method, adjusting the data with the categories of translation method, determining the categorization of the translation equivalence, organizing an explanation for each finding, and the final step is interpreting and concluding the analysis result. The finding results of hyperbolic expressions used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 official webpages are single-word hyperbole, phrasal hyperbole, clausal hyperbole, numerical hyperbole, superlative hyperbole, comparison hyperbole, and repetition hyperbole. Translation methods applied in iPhone 14 iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 official webpages are word-for-word translation, literal translation, faithful translation, semantic translation, adaptation translation, free translation, idiomatic translation, and communicative translation. Translation equivalence strategy used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 is foreignization. The translator deliberately carries the culture of the source language into the target language to introduce the foreign product to the local society through the description on the webpages.

Keywords: Hyperbole, Hyperbolic Expression, Translation, Iphone Official Webpage, Translation Equivalence

1. Introduction

The existence of translation activity is an essential intermediary in defining many objects into different language forms. Nida and Taber (1974) explained that an optimum translation is a translation that sounds naturally that is not perceived through the translation process. Furthermore, it can fulfill the needs of the target readers who hold a right to receive a good quality translation result (Salsabila, R. & Jumanto, J., 2020). The presence of connection among countries and languages causes a translation to endure a significant role in cultural transmission so that when an unstable situation appears, the result of translation would deviate and be biased (Newmark, 1988). Aspects

of translation practices that should be considered into significant accounts among others are translation methods and translation equivalence.

1.1. Translation Method

Translation method is a particular procedure to translate a thing based on a specific translation plan (Anshori, 2010). Based on the definition, recognizing the translation method is significant to find out the way used by the translator in conveying the message universally and thoroughly of the source language into the target language. Each decision for the translation chosen by the translator would produce several options that can be applied so that it can affect the entire translation result (Molina & Albir, 2002). Newmark constructed a diagram to categorize the translation method into two types. The first is the methods that accentuates the source language, and the second is accentuated into target language. The category of the translation method is depicted through the V-diagram in Figure 1.

Figure 1: V-diagram of Translation Method by Newmark (1988)

1.2. Translation Equivalence

Venuti (2004) claimed that equivalence contains some variables that can identify equality between two different foreign messages, there are exactness, sufficiency, precision, correspondence, identity, and faithfully. Equivalence is possible to remove the existence of diversion in translation. The process starts with a comparison between the information and the making of response with the production through the target language and its culture. The equivalence message eventually depends on the identity of the situation. It is a possible thing to do that target language can preserve the reality of particular characteristics unknown by the source language (Vinay & Darbelnet, cited by Venuti, 2004).

Foreignization is an equivalence that takes side dominantly with the Source Language (SL). This translation is more accentuated regarding the language form and the genuineness of the grammatical of the source text rather than the target text (Venuti, cited by Oktafiana & Wibisono, 2020). Siregar (2016) defined that an accurate and acceptable translation is appropriate with the urge of the readers who expect the existence of SL culture or the language of the first writer as the embodiment of the culture within the translation is substantial for the society. Lezkovar (cited by Oktafiana & Wibisono 2020) also considered that foreignization processes an attempt to maintain a prevalent and unique culture of the SL even though it is unacceptable for the Target Language (TL). Moreover, the method of foreignization would be completely unfree from the domestic points and orders, including the growth of culture in the nation (Nott, cited by Venuti, 2004).

Domestication is an equality strategy that the accurate and acceptable translation belongs to the cultural society of TL. As a result, the translation would be unseen as a translation. Therefore, the translator is free to decide the necessity of the translation. Therefore, it does not turn out as foreign work (Siregar, 2016). Moreover, domestication is an equivalence that sided with the TL. This type of translation is more consider with the readability of the reader of the target text which is more concentrated on the grammatical and the message delivery style of the target text rather than the source text (Venuti, cited in Oktafiana & Wibisono, 2020). Arnold (cited by Venuti, 2004) recommends using a free domestication to produce a fluent and familiar that respects the moral value of the bourgeois in which the difference between foreign text and culture is disappeared because the translator has already omitted it.

Anshori (2010) defined that there is a connection between the translation method proposed by Newmark (1988) with the theory of foreignization and domestication proposed by Venuti (2004) as follows:

- 1) Foreignization use terms and words which “borrow” from the source of the language. Therefore, it is regarding word-for-word translation, literal translation, faithful translation, and semantic translation.
- 2) Domestication use the terms and words that “change” to the target language. Hence, it is related to adaptation translation, free translation, idiomatic translation, and communicative translation.

1.3. Hyperbole

Hyperbole is an object of aesthetic and rhetorical devices which offers an instrument to create something perceptible into imperceptible and something ordinary into extraordinary (Berlyne, cited by Barbu & Kleitsch, 2015). The effects generated by hyperbole are humorous, persuasive, and intuitive role. Another possible effect is a frightening reaction to something exaggerated as the embodiment of confusion (Barbu & Kleitsch, 2015). Claridge (2011) explained the hyperbole into seven categorizes, there are single-word hyperbole, phrasal hyperbole, clausal hyperbole, numerical hyperbole, superlative hyperbole, comparison hyperbole, and repetition hyperbole.

This study centered on analyzing the translation method and the categorization of equivalence of hyperbolic expressions within the English-Indonesian translation of iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, iPhone SE 2022 official webpages. Several theories applied in this study are the theory of translation equivalence by Venuti (2004), the translation method by Newmark (1988), and the categorization of hyperbolic expressions by Claridge (2011). The data source is taken from iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, iPhone SE 2022 official webpages. The data of this study are the hyperbolic expressions used in the English-Indonesian translation of iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, iPhone SE 2022 official webpages.

This study was conducted to identify the types of hyperbole, describe the translation by recognizing the translation equivalence whether it is foreignization or domestication through the translation methods, and explain the differences of the hyperbolic expression translation in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 official webpages. The researcher preferred to use several webpages of iPhone as the webpages not only present the original version of the description which is in English, but also show its translation, one of which is Indonesian. Furthermore, the researcher found one of phenomena about the translation methods used by the translator in translating the hyperbolic expressions, the finding example of which is pictured in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 2: English Version Screenshot of Hyperbolic Expression of iPhone 14 Pro Official Webpage

Source: <https://www.apple.com/iphone-14>

Figure 3: Indonesian Version Screenshot of Hyperbolic Expression of iPhone 14 Pro Official Webpage

Source: <https://www.apple.com/id/iphone-14>

According to the pictures above, a hyperbolic expression found in iPhone 14 Pro official webpage was “*The picture of versatility*” and translated into “*Selalu indah. Serba bisa*”. As known in the source language and the target

language above, both of them have highly distinct word structures and slightly similar meaning. In terms of structure, *the picture of versatility* is a noun phrase. Meanwhile, *Selalu indah. Serba bisa* is the combination of two adjective phrases. In the target language, the translator did not translate the noun phrase *the picture* and used the adjective phrase *selalu indah* as a replacement. Both forms are very dissimilar. Moreover, although the noun *versatility* and the adjective phrase *serba bisa* has quite the same meaning which is related to the ability in conducting many things, it is obvious that both have very distinct structure and way to transfer the message to the target reader.

The implementation of hyperbole by the writer is to create an overstate situation so that the literature produces a dramatic sense and increases attractiveness within the work. Thus, in terms of translation, the consideration in selecting the word becomes significant so that the message and the hyperbolic effect are still maintained and be well-delivered to the target language (Wahyuni & Pradhana, 2017). On the whole, identifying the equivalence of the translation through analyzing the translation methods of hyperbolic expressions used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 official webpages is essential to understand the partiality of the translator in delivering the message within these webpages. Concerning whether it would fulfill the necessity of the target reader or stand consistently on the side of the source language and its culture.

The other related studies are entitled *The Equivalence of Figurative Language Used in English and Indonesian Versions of Songs “Be Careful with my Heart (Tetaplah di Hatiku)” and “Denpasar Moon” created by Sahaduta & Nugroho (2013) conducted by Sahaduta & Nugroho (2013)*. The differences identified in this study is that figurative language, especially hyperbole, is only analyzed in general. Moreover, the category of translation equivalence did not mention the source appropriately, and the examination process of translation equivalence is not explained elaborately. Moreover, another study is entitled “A Translation Analysis of Superlative Form of Hyperbolic Expressions in The Novel Entitled “The Adventure of Sherlock Holmes by Sir Arthur Conan Doyle” by Yamananda (2016). A most recent study is done by Jumanto et al. (2022), which observes the performances of online translation machines through figurative language involvement. Jumanto et al. (2022) terms the figurative language with its denotative meaning as *metalanguage* which is based on human creative imagination. However, besides all the studies mentioned, the research gap found in this study is that the researcher assessed the translation quality using a theory from Nababan. In rating the quality, the researcher involved particular raters in determining the quality of the translation. The translation technique analyzed in this research is the translation technique by Molina and Albir (2022). The researcher used the theory of hyperbolic expressions from Cano Mora (2009) and focused more on the superlative degree within the collected data.

2. Method

This study applied a qualitative method as this method is appropriate for the purpose that the researcher want to achieve. Moreover, this method also can be conducted to coincide with the data collection process so that this study would be possible to develop flexibly and produce the data in many forms. The data sources is taken from iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, iPhone SE 2022 official webpages on October 2022, which can be accessed on <https://www.apple.com/iphone-14/> and <https://www.apple.com/id/iphone-14/> (English and Indonesian version of iPhone 14 official webpage), <https://www.apple.com/iphone-14-pro/> and <https://www.apple.com/id/iphone-14-pro/> (English and Indonesian version of iPhone 14 Pro official webpage), and <https://www.apple.com/iphone-se/> and <https://www.apple.com/id/iphone-se/> (English and Indonesian version of iPhone SE 2022 official webpage). In collecting the data, the researcher accessed the official webpages of iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 and read the source data thoroughly to find the appropriate data for the research. After the source data was all-scanned, the researcher continued by finding the form of hyperbolic expressions according to Claridge (2011) in the original version (English) and the translation version (Indonesian) in the form of words, phrases, clauses, and sentences appropriately. The data findings are analyzed one after one by adjusting with the categories of translation method proposed by Newmark (1988), then determined the categorization of the translation equivalence, whether it is foreignization or domestication. It is would be categorized as a foreignization if the translator dominantly used the translation methods based on the source language accentuation. Meanwhile, it would be categorized as a domestication if the translator mainly applied the translation methods based on the target language accentuation.

3. Results

The researcher found hyperbolic expressions used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 official webpages in several forms according to the category of hyperbole by Claridge (2011). Thoroughly, the finding result of the hyperbolic expressions within the webpages are 75 expressions. There are 22 hyperbolic expressions on iPhone 14 webpage, 21 hyperbolic expressions on iPhone 14 Pro webpage, and 32 hyperbolic expressions on iPhone SE 2022 official webpage. Furthermore, based on the hyperbolic expression findings, the researcher continued by determined the translation method used by the translator according to Newmark (1988) individually. The finding or the result on the quantity and percentage of hyperbolic expressions within the three websites is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Quantity and Percentage of Hyperbolic Expressions used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 Official Webpages

Types of Hyperbole	iPhone 14		iPhone 14 Pro		iPhone SE 2022	
	Qty	%	Qty	%	Qty	%
Single-word Hyperbole	9	40	6	28	14	44
Phrasal Hyperbole	3	14	8	38	12	37
Clausal Hyperbole	0	0	1	5	1	3
Numerical Hyperbole	0	0	1	5	1	3
Superlative Hyperbole	7	32	4	19	4	13
Comparison Hyperbole	2	9	1	5	0	0
Repetition Hyperbole	1	5	0	0	0	0
Total	22	100	21	100	32	100

The total findings of hyperbole types used in iPhone 14 which is 22 hyperbole expressions, single-word hyperbole is the highest amount of hyperbole types which appeared nine times (40%). Afterward, followed by superlative hyperbole which appeared seven times (32%), phrasal hyperbole which appeared three times (14%), comparison hyperbole which appeared two times (9%), repetition hyperbole which appeared one time (5%), and the lowest amount of hyperbole types are held by clausal and numerical hyperbole in which these types did not appear in iPhone 14 official webpage. The hyperbolic expressions used in iPhone 14 Pro official webpage is 21 expressions. The highest amount of hyperbole types used in iPhone 14 Pro official webpages is phrasal hyperbole in which each type totaling eight times appeared (38%), the second position is single-word hyperbole which appeared six times (28%), the third position is superlative hyperbole which appeared four times (19%), and the fourth position consists of three types of hyperbole which is clausal hyperbole, numerical hyperbole, and comparison hyperbole in which each type appeared one time (5%). Moreover, repetition hyperbole has not appeared in the findings of hyperbolic expressions used in iPhone 14 Pro official webpages. Meanwhile, the hyperbolic expressions found in iPhone SE 2022 official webpages is 32 expressions. As identical as the finding amount of iPhone 14 and iPhone 14 Pro official webpages, the types of hyperbole that often appeared are single-word hyperbole which appeared 14 times (44%). The second most appeared hyperbole type is phrasal hyperbole which is 12 times (37%). Henceforth, the third most appeared hyperbole type is superlative hyperbole which is four times (13%), and the fourth most appeared hyperbole type are clausal hyperbole and numerical hyperbole which are one time (3%) for each type. Subsequently, comparison and repetition hyperbole are not applicable to iPhone SE 2022 official webpage.

The bold parts on each webpage indicate the most frequently appeared and used of hyperbole type used in the webpages. In iPhone 14 and iPhone SE 2022 official webpages, single-word hyperbole is the dominant type applied. In accordance with Claridge's theory, single-word hyperbole is the most ordinary realization in which only a word causes exaggeration within a content. Moreover, this type has a particular impact. It is when the word is omitted the exaggerated effect also disappears. In the meantime, on iPhone 14 Pro official webpage, the most

frequently emerged is phrasal hyperbole. This type contains universal forms in which the hyperbole can be made in any word and sense. Claridge (2011) denoted that phrasal hyperbole is possibly arranged by other formats such as a number, superlative form, or any global descriptor.

Furthermore, the quantity and percentage of each method of translation applied in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 official webpages can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Quantity and Percentage of Translation Methods applied in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 Official Webpages

Translation Method	iPhone 14		iPhone 14 Pro		iPhone SE (2022)	
	Qty	%	Qty	%	Qty	%
Word-for-Word Translation	5	23	3	15	9	28
Literal Translation	6	27	4	19	3	9
Faithful Translation	5	23	4	19	3	9
Semantic Translation	4	19	4	19	9	28
Adaptation Translation	1	4	2	9	1	4
Free Translation	0	0	2	9	4	13
Idiomatic Translation	0	0	1	5	0	0
Communicative Translation	1	4	1	5	3	9
Total	22	100	21	100	32	100

The translator dominantly used the literal translation method as the translation method applied six times (27%) for each method in translating the hyperbolic expressions of iPhone 14 official webpages. Subsequently, the word for word translation and faithful translation were applied five times (23%) for each method, the semantic translation was applied four times (19%), the adaptation and communicative translation was applied only one time (4%) for each method. In the meantime, the free translation, and the idiomatic translation were not used by the translator in translating hyperbolic expressions of the iPhone 14 official webpage. Moreover, in translating the hyperbolic expressions of iPhone 14 Pro, the translator frequently applied the literal, semantic, and faithful translation in delivering the hyperbolic expressions of iPhone 14 Pro as it was used five times (19%) for each method. Afterward, the word-for-word translation was applied three times (15%), the free translation was applied two times (9%), the adaptation translation, the idiomatic translation and the communicative translation were also only applied one time (5%) for each method. Different from iPhone 14 and 14 Pro, the translator mostly applied the word-for-word translation and the semantic translation in translating hyperbolic expressions of iPhone SE 2022 which appeared nine times (28%) for each method. Thereafter, the free translation was applied four times (10%), the literal translation, the faithful translation, and the communicative translation were applied three times (9%) for each method, and the adaptation translation was applied one time (4%). Meanwhile, the idiomatic translation was not preferred by the translator to translate the hyperbolic expressions of iPhone SE 2022.

4. Discussion

This research indicates that the translator is truly accentuating the source language as the methods that emphasize the viewpoint of the source language reached higher than the other one. The researcher considers that the decision chosen by the translator indicated wisdom and carefulness in delivering the message. Besides, the translator recognized that the data sources hold much information and is attractively delivered since it was in the form of an advertisement. Hence, the translator attempted to keep the meaning of the source language almost thoroughly rather than misinformation occurring in the translation result.

4.1. Types of Hyperbole used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 Official Webpages

Based on Claridge (2011), each type of hyperbole found in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 official webpages is described and accounted for below.

4.1.1 Single-word Hyperbole

Single-word hyperbole can be identified when there is any particular word that gives an exaggerated term within the context. Meanwhile, when the exaggerated word is deleted, it would go back to an ordinary context.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone 14 Official Webpage)

A magical new way to interact with iPhone

The word *magical* is another example of single-word hyperbole applied to the data found. According to Merriam-Webster Dictionaries, something that describes as magical, it is explained that the thing is extremely pleasant, inspiring, or enjoyable. The word *magical* represents an overstatement as the expression depicts that the new way to interact with iPhone is highly pleasurable. In case that the word *magical* is removed, probably it only shows a new way to interact with iPhone regularly. Therefore, it indicates that a single-word hyperbole is only a word that gives a huge impact within a particular context.

4.1.2 Phrasal Hyperbole

Phrasal hyperbole is a combination of hyperbole between senses and words. It usually appears in several kinds of phrases. The phrase that often comes up in hyperbolic meaning is a noun phrase (NP).

Excerpt (taken from iPhone 14 Pro Official Webpage)

An innovative 48MP camera for mind-blowing detail

Based on the structure, the phrase *mind-blowing detail* is a form of a noun phrase (NP) in which the adjective *mind-blowing* is a pre-modifier and the noun *detail* is the head. The NP *mind-blowing detail* is also a creative NP which is creatively converted from the standard NP *detail which blows the mind* (cf. Jumanto, 2017). Moreover, based on Oxford Learner's Dictionaries, the adjective *mind-blowing* is an extremely interesting and surprising feeling about a certain thing. The excerpt above explains the ability of the 48MP camera which is able to produce a very impressive detail of the picture.

4.1.3 Clausal Hyperbole

According to Claridge (2011), clausal hyperbole is formed as a combination of the two or more constituents of a clause. During analyze the types of hyperbole used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 official webpages, the researcher merely found one expression which evidenced a clausal hyperbole.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone SE 2022 Official Webpage)

The Retina HD display makes everything look incredible

This excerpt is categorized as a clausal hyperbole since the structure is in the form of a clause which becomes elucidatory of *the Retina HD display*. According to Oxford Learner's Dictionaries, the word *incredible* is an adjective that explains something that can be extremely good. In the context, the clausal hyperbole *everything looks incredible* functions to describe the performance of *the Retina HD display* which can create the maximum result so that everything that appears from the display looks in excellent quality. The adjective *incredible* is a highly effective way of presenting an exaggerated effect within the text.

4.1.4 Numerical Hyperbole

Numerical hyperbole is a type of hyperbole in which numbers has a big role to create exaggerated expressions on a larger-scale (Claridge, 2011). The use of numerical terms such as hundreds, thousands, etc., causes an effective and conspicuous exaggeration within a particular context without any detailed context needed.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone 14 Pro Official Webpage)

Putting tons of framing flexibility in your pocket.

The word *ton* indicates a numerical hyperbole as *ton* is part of a weight measurement. Based on Oxford Learners Dictionaries, *tons* can be applied in an informal form that can describe something in a high quantity. In the expressions above, the word *ton* represents the numerous flexible abilities in taking a picture with the camera.

4.1.5 Superlative Hyperbole

Superlative hyperbole is related to relativity in high potency (Claridge, 2011). Bolinger (in Claridge, 2011) defined that the superlative can bounce the scale of any adjective out of the limits.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone 14 Official Webpage)

Cinematic mode automatically shifts focus to the most important subject in a scene, just like filmmakers do.

The researcher highlighted the phrase *the most important subject in a scene* as a form of superlative. It can be characterized by determiner *the most* which based on Oxford Learner's Dictionaries, is defined as showing a number or amount in the largest degree. According to the expressions, the phrase *the most important subject in a scene* as a perfect, standard, M-H-M NP with *the most important* as pre-modifier and *in a scene* as post-modifier to the head *subject* (cf. Jumanto, 2017) has a role as an emphasis on the ability of the cinematic mode feature in which the feature can capture the most substantial object in the camera. Moreover, the phrase also works as an attraction to the target buyer who regularly wants to take their best and most significant picture.

4.1.6 Comparison Hyperbole

Comparison hyperbole is characterized as non-metaphorical comparison and using a comparative device such as the word *than*, *as*, or *like*. Claridge (2011) explained that the rule of comparison hyperbole enables to compare two entities which are totally impossible or are creating an impossibility result. Furthermore, conducting a comparison caused the entity being maximum.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone 14 Official Webpage)

Home movies that look like Hollywood movies

The comparison hyperbole in the finding known by the phrase *look like Hollywood movies*. As mentioned before, the preposition *like* indicates a comparative article that has meaning to show an equation between two particular entities. Moreover, the comparative phrase *look like Hollywood movies* is intended to represent that the ability of the iPhone in making videos has the best quality so that it can be equated with Hollywood movies. Whereas, creating a Hollywood movie is not effortless work. It certainly requires a lot of jobs that are impossible to easily follow by the capability of a phone. Therefore, the comparative phrase above definitely compares two things that are resulting in an impossibility.

4.1.7 Repetition Hyperbole

According to Claridge (2011), repetition form in hyperbole is the simplest way to say that something is more than another. It is conducted by restating the same thing several times without any interruption. Moreover, repetition creates something more significant and communicatively engaging. In this study, the researcher only identified one repetition of hyperbole within the data source.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone 14 Official Webpage)

Big and bigger

Repetition form is found in the adjective *big* which means something in the large size, amount, or degree. The repetitive expressions *big and bigger* are used to explain the particular size and emphasize the length of the iPhone.

4.2. Translation Method of Hyperbolic Expressions used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 Official Webpages

After identifying hyperbolic expressions in the data source, the researcher continued to examine the method applied in the translation of iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 official webpages. Hence, the description of the analysis result about the use of the translation method would be interpreted below.

4.2.1 Word-for-word Translation

Nababan (as cited in Anshori, 2010) explained that fundamentally, the word-for-word translation method is tightly bound to word structure. In translating, the translator only finds the equivalent word of the source language in the target language without altering the word structure within the translation.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone SE 2022 Official Webpage)

SL: The Retina HD display makes everything look incredible

TL: *Layar Retina HD membuat segalanya tampak luar biasa*

Another example of word-for-word translation is the hyperbolic expressions *everything look incredible* translated according to the structure of the source language into *segalanya tampak luar biasa*. In this process, the translator translated the message as equal to the sequence of the word in the source language. In the translation, *everything* is translated into *segalanya*, *look* is translated into *tampak*, and *incredible* is translated into *luar biasa*. Even though the expressions is translated structurally into the target language, the meaning of the source language is still easy to be understood by the reader of the target language.

4.2.2. Literal Translation

Anshori (2010) elucidated in the beginning that a literal translation is conducted similarly to word-for-word translation, but then, the translator attempted to adjust the wording of the translation with the wording of the target language. This method is applied when the sentence structure of the source language is distinct from the sentence structure of the target language.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone 14 Pro Official Webpage)

SL: The most secure facial authentication in a smartphone

TL: *Autentikasi wajah paling aman di ponsel pintar*

This is an example of how the translator translated the source text into the target text literally as every word is translated appropriately but in terms of the structure, the translator changed into the target language viewpoint. It can be identified by the difference in the structure that occurred in both the source language and the target language. In the source language, the structure of the phrase consists of article + pre-modifier (adjective) + head (noun) in which the article *the*, the pre-modifier *most secure*, and the noun head *facial authentication*. Meanwhile, in the phrase structure of the target language, Maryono (2010) explained that one of the structures of the noun phrase is (noun + noun) + adjective. (Noun + noun) functions as a center, and the adjective function as an attribute. In the target language, *autentikasi wajah* is a center which is (noun + noun), and *paling aman* is an attribute which is an adjective.

4.2.3. Faithful Translation

Newmark (1988) defined that faithful translation is conducted to create a meaning contextually of a source language. Moreover, Puspita (2020) elucidated that to translate faithfully, the translator needs to deliver the meaning of cultural words and at the same time retain the grammatical and lexical aspects of the source language within the translation. Flora (as cited in Puspita 2020) explained that faithful translation is when a translator attempts to maintain the meaning of the sentence but it is changeable and related to the context.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone SE 2022 Official Webpage)

SL: Almost 1.8 million awe-inspiring apps

TL: *Hampir 1,8 juta aplikasi yang menginspirasi*

Andrian (2014) explained that faithful translation is a translation that endeavors to retain the aspect of the format in the source language to exist in the target language so that the reader can still notice completely the faithful of the word used in the target language. It can be identified through excerpt 3 that the hyperbole expressions *awe-*

inspiring is translated into *menginspirasi*. According to Oxford Learner's Dictionary, *awe-inspiring* means to express admiration greatly for a certain thing. Here, the translator delivered the message from the source language into the target language faithfully since the word form of *menginspirasi* is the most loyal to the hyperbolic expressions *awe-inspiring*.

4.2.4. Semantic Translation

Semantic translation is related to aesthetical form and flexibility of the translation result. Newmark (1988) emphasized that semantic translation should regard the beauty and natural component within the source language even sacrificing the literal meaning. In the excerpt above, the researcher described how semantic translation is applied in translating the hyperbolic expressions by the translator.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone 14 Official Webpage)

SL: High resolution and color accuracy make everything look sharp and true to life

TL: *Resolusi dan akurasi warna yang tinggi menjadikan semuanya terlihat tajam dan begitu hidup.*

According to Oxford Learner's Dictionaries, the phrasal hyperbole *true to life* is categorized as an idiomatic form that expresses that an invention seems tangible. Furthermore, the translation in the target language *begitu hidup* also an expression to show an aesthetic value as it explains that *hidup* means something remains, exists, and does not disappear. Both the source text and the target text contain an aesthetic expressions and quite identical meaning. Similar to the explanation before, although the phrasal hyperbole *true to life* is an idiom. However, the idiomatic form was not maintained by the translator in the translation result and could not be classified as an idiomatic translation. Hence, the researcher decided that the method used in translating the hyperbole is a semantic translation.

4.2.5. Adaptation Translation

Newmark (1988) elucidated that adaptation translation is the method the translator delivers the message by converting the cultural meaning of the source language to the cultural meaning of the target language. Moreover, Anshori (2010) considered that adaptation translation is a type of translation method in which the meaning of the target language is freest and closest to the message of the target language.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone SE 2022 Official Webpage)

SL: A camera you'll instantly click with.

TL: *Kamera yang langsung klik dengan Anda.*

The excerpt is identified as the adaptation translation as the source language and the target language have different terms. According to Collins Dictionaries, *instantly* is an adverb of manner arranged from the countable noun *instant* + *ly* in which *instant* explain a certain period in an extremely short time. In the target language, the adverb *instantly* was translated into *yang langsung* in which *yang* is a conjunction, and *langsung* is an adverb that means something comes without any intermediary and stopping. In terms of contextual meaning, *instantly* and *yang langsung* have a similar meaning which is to explain something immediately. Even though both terms are expressed in different cultural words, the meaning of the term was well-delivered to the target reader.

4.2.6. Free Translation

Newmark (1988) elucidated that free translation is conducted by creating the meaning without considering the form of the source language. This method allows the translator to sharpen the creativity in delivering the meaning of the source language to the target language.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone SE 2022 Official Webpage)

SL: Music, made magic

TL: *Musik semakin merdu*

The excerpt is identified as a free translation as the target language is translated freely from the source language. In the source language, *made magic* means an activity to create something in the sense of sorcery (Collins Dictionaries, 2022). In relation to the context, it means the iPhone SE 2022 can elevate the music in a better way in which it is portrayed as magic. According to Oxford Learner's Dictionary, *magic* means a certain high quality

or the ability of something so that the noun *magic* can produce an extra meaning for the product. Furthermore, in the target language, the expression *semakin merdu* has closely related to the music. *Semakin* is an adverb that means an action to escalate, and *Merdu* means something pleasant to hear. Contextually, *semakin merdu* shows that the music produced by the iPhone SE 2022 would sound better. The translation of the hyperbole *made magic* into *semakin merdu* is also a creative human translation that no translation machine can probably do, which transfers the metalanguage (connotation) *made magic* into the object language (denotation) *semakin merdu* (see: Jumanto et al., 2022). Thus, although both languages have their own way of delivering the message without any relation in terms of diction, their intended meaning was equal and delivered appropriately.

4.2.7 Idiomatic Translation

According to Puspita (2020), idiomatic translation is a translation that is related to the expressions of an idiom that appeared in the source language and the target language. In the process of the translation, Anshori (2010) explained that in the translation process, the translator reproduces the message of the source language which contains a familiarity effect and idiomatic expressions in which not obtained from the source language.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone 14 Pro Official Webpage)

SL: See why the new Super Retina XDR display is like nothing else.

TL: Lihat mengapa layar Super Retina XDR baru tidak ada duanya.

According to Oxford Learner's Dictionaries, the idiom *like nothing else* means nothing another action can do except the one mentioned. Furthermore, Puspita (2020) explained that idiomatic expressions should be delivered into the idiomatic expressions as well. In the target text, the translator translated the idiom *like nothing else* into another idiom that is *tidak ada duanya*. The idiom *tidak ada duanya* means nothing for the second option. Hence, it has a similar meaning to the idiom *like nothing else*, so it can be categorized as an idiomatic translation.

4.2.8 Communicative Translation

Andrian (2014) explained that communicative translation is a translation in which the meaning of the message is a significant aspect yet does not have to translate freely. In accordance with the title, communicative translation absolutely pays attention to the communicative principle which is the reader and the purpose of the translation.

Excerpt (taken from iPhone 14 Official Webpage)

SL: Our longest battery life ever

TL: Baterai kami yang paling tahan lama

The communicative translation involves the point of view of the target reader so that the purpose of the message would be well-received by the target reader. In this excerpt, the expression *our longest battery life ever* wants to present that the battery life of the iPhone 14 has the biggest power. Meanwhile, in the target language, the term *longest* is rarely used to describe something in terms of durability. In the translation, the use of the term *tahan lama* which means to explain something in a long-lasting was a proper decision by the translator to deliver the meaning of *longest battery life* instead of maintaining the literal meaning. Accordingly, the message of the source language is already conveyed communicatively in the target language.

4.3. Translation Equivalence of Hyperbolic Expressions used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 Official Webpages

The researcher attempted to adjust and summarize the result of the analysis of the translation method of hyperbolic expressions used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 Official Websites to discover the equivalence degrees of the translation. Table 3 presents the equivalence degrees of the three webpages.

Table 3: The Equivalence Degrees of the Translation Methods of Hiperbolic Expressions Used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022 Official Webpages

	Translation Method	iPhone 14	iPhone 14 Pro	iPhone SE 2022
Foreignization	Word-for-word	23%	15%	28%
	Translation			
	Literal Translation	27%	19%	9%

	Faithful Translation	23%	19%	9%
	Semantic Translation	19%	19%	28%
Total		92%	72%	74%
	Adaptation Translation	4%	9%	4%
	Free Translation	0%	9%	13%
Domestication	Idiomatic Translation	0%	5%	0%
	Communicative Translation	4%	5%	9%
Total		8%	28%	26%

The translator tended to use the foreignization strategy to translate the hyperbolic expressions used in iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022. It indicates that all of the webpages are more accentuated and are on the side of the source language rather than the target language. Thus, it also can be perceived that the translator was highly considered of the language form and the genuineness of the grammatical of the source language. In terms of cultural value, it can be seen that the products are globally produced that affect the way to market, one is through the advertisement on the webpage. A probability that might cause the translator to tend to foreignization is the translator deliberately carries the culture of the source language into the target language. It is because the translator has a role as a bridge to introduce the foreign product to the local society through the explanation on the webpages since the products are world widely sold. Thus, the translator attempted to maintain the culture that existed in the source language to the target language, so one of the main purposes of the company can be achieved. Some risks might happen to the target reader. The target readers who do not care about the method used by the translator to deliver the meaning would not have bothered by the language phenomenon since they only focus on the product offered. Meanwhile, for the target readers who are concerned by the language things or require some further explanations through the webpages, it might bring up misconception and confusion by them to understand the intention of the source language. Therefore, it depends on the translator about how the meaning should be conveyed appropriately to the target reader.

The entire types of hyperbole according to Claridge (2011) such as single-word hyperbole, phrasal hyperbole, clausal hyperbole, numerical hyperbole, superlative hyperbole, comparison hyperbole, and repetition hyperbole appeared within the official webpages of iPhone 14, iPhone 14 Pro, and iPhone SE 2022. The translation method applied by the translator was dominantly based on the source language accentuation such as word-for-word translation, literal translation, faithful translation, and semantic translation. Therefore, the translation equivalence regarding to the most applied methods is foreignization. The translator intentionally brings the culture of the source language or the foreign language into the target language or the local language to introduce the foreign product specifications to the local society through the description of the products in the webpages.

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References

- Aditiawan, R. T. (2020). Penggunaan Frasa Nomina dalam Surat Kabar Jawa Pos: Kontruksi Frasa Nomina [Use of Noun Phrases in Jawa Pos Newspaper]. *Belajar bahasa: jurnal ilmiah program studi pendidikan bahasa dan sastra Indonesia, Volume 5*, (2), 221-232. DOI: 10.32528/bb.v5i2.3243
- Aljadaan, N. (2018). Understanding Hyperbole. *Arab World English Journal*, October 2018, 1-31. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/th.212>
- Anshori, S. (2010). Teknik, Metode, dan Ideologi Penerjemahan Buku Economic Concepts of Ibn Timiyah” ke dalam Bahasa Indonesia dan Dampaknya Pada Kualitas Terjemahan [Techniques, Methods, and Ideologies in the Translation of the Book “Economic Concepts of Ibn Timiyah” into Indonesian and the Effects on Translation Quality]. *A Master's Thesis*. Universitas Sebelas Maret Surakarta, 2010. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/12348182.pdf>
- Barbu-Kleitch, Oana. (2015). Use of Hyperboles in Advertising Effectiveness. *International Conference RCIC'15: Redefining Community in International Context*. Brasov, 21-23 May 2015, pp. 175-184. <https://www.afahc.ro/ro/rcic/2015/rcic'15/PC/Barbu-Kleitsch.pdf>
- Chen, S. Y. (2014). Bilingual Advertising in Melbourne Chinatown. *Journal of International Students*, Volume 4, (4), 389-396. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32674/jis.v4i4.457>
- Claridge, C. (2011). *Hyperbole in English* (M. Kyto, Ed.). Cambridge University Press. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511779480>
- Cook, G. (2001). *The Discourse of Advertising* (2nd Edition). United Kingdom: Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research Design Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (V. Knight, S. Connelly, L. Habib, S. K. Quensenberry, & M. P. Scott, Eds.; 3rd Edition). New York: SAGE Publications.
- Fan, Y. (2013, December). The Lexical Features of English Advertisement. *Proceedings of the 2013 International Conference on the Modern Development of Humanities and Social Science*. Dordrecht: Atlantis Press.
- Goddard, A. (2001). *The Language of Advertising* (R. Carter & A. Goddard, Eds.). Great Britain: Taylor & Francis e-Library.
- Jumanto, Jumanto. (2017). *Noun Phrases: A Set of Comprehensive Facts and Some Theoretical Tendencies* (Second Edition). Yogyakarta: Morfalingua. ISBN/ISSN. 978-602-60133-3-0.
- Jumanto, J., Nugroho, R. A., & Basari, A. (2018). Pragmatics and Translation: A Preliminary Study. *Shaping New Understandings in ELT*, 17-26. Malaysia: Universiti Putra Malaysia. https://spel3.upm.edu.my/max/dokumen/MICELT_MICELT_2018_-_PROCEEDINGS.pdf
- Jumanto, J., Asmarani, R., Rizal, S. S., Sulistyorini, H. (2022). The Discrepancies of Online Translation-Machine Performances: A Mini-Test on Object Language and Metalanguage. *2022 International Seminar on Application for Technology of Information and Communication (iSemantic)*, Semarang, Indonesia, 2022, pp. 27-35, doi: 10.1109/iSemantic55962.2022.9920394. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9920394>.
- Keraf, G. (1991). *Diksi dan Gaya Bahasa* (7th Edition). Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Kilian, F. R. (2019). The English - Indonesian Translation Analysis of Figurative Language in the Novel “To Kill a Mockingbird” by Harper Lee. *JELLT*, 3, (2), 57-68. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36597/jellt.v3i2.5995>
- Maryono. (2010). Frasa Nomina yang Terdiri dari Tiga Kata dalam Bahasa Indonesia [Noun Phrases with Three Words in Indonesian]. *A Master's Thesis*. Universitas Sanata Dharma, 2010. <https://repository.usd.ac.id/25502/>
- Mc Millan, J., & Schumacher, S. (2014). *Research in Education Evidence-Based Inquiry* (7th Edition). London: Pearson Education Limited. <https://files.pearsoned.de/ps/ext/9781292035871>
- Molina, L., & Albir, A. H. (2002). Translation Technique Revisited: A Dynamic and functionalist Approach. Barcelona: Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. https://ddd.uab.cat/pub/artpub/2002/137439/meta_a2002v47n4p498.pdf
- Newmark, P. (1988). *A Textbook of Translation* (1st Edition). Rome, Italy: Prentice Hall.
- Nida, E. A., & Taber, C. R. (1982). *The Theory and Practice of Translation* (Vol. 8). Leiden: E.J Brill.
- Nugraha, A., Nugroho, M. A. B., & Rahman, Y. (2017). English - Indonesian Translation Methods in the Short Story “A Blunder” by Anton Chekhov. *Indonesian EFL Journal*, 3, (1), 79-86. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.25134/ieflij.v3i1.656>
- Oktafiana, Y., & Wibisono, G. (2020). Ekuivalensi Terjemahan Subtitle Film Better Days 《少年的你》 Versi Bahasa Mandarin (Bs) Dengan Versi Bahasa Indonesia (Bs). *Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa Mandarin Unesa* [Translation Equivalence of the Film Subtitle Better Days of the Mandarin Version (SL) and the Indonesian Version (TL)], 3, (2), 1-15. <https://ejournal.unesa.ac.id/index.php/manadarin/article/view/46836>
- Prajutha, R. (2010). Domestication and Foreignization Strategies on Translated Novel of “The Tales of Beedle the Bard”. An Undergraduate's Thesis. Malang: Universitas Brawijaya. <http://repository.ub.ac.id/id/eprint/100307/>

- Purnastuti, L. (2004). Perdagangan Elektronik: Suatu Bentuk Pasar Baru yang Menjanjikan? [E-Commerce: A New Form of Promising Market?]. *Jurnal Ekonomi & Pendidikan*, 1, (1), 10-22. <https://journal.uny.ac.id/index.php/jep/article/view/669/533>
- Puspita, A. T. (2020). The Use of Newmark Translation Methods in English to Indonesian Rendering of Austen's Emma. *An Undergraduate's Thesis*. Semarang: Universitas Negeri Semarang. <http://lib.unnes.ac.id/41252/>
- Sahaduta, Y., & Nugroho, R. A. (2013). The Equivalence of Figurative Language used in English and Indonesian Versions of Songs "Be Careful with My Heart (Tetaplah di Hatiku)" and "Denpasar Moon." *An Undergraduate's Thesis*. Semarang: Universitas Dian Nuswantoro. <https://repository.dinus.ac.id/>
- Salsabila, R., & Jumanto, J. (2020). Translation Strategies for Cultural Expressions in Garuda Indonesia's Inflight Magazine "Colors." *Journal BASIS*, 7, (1), 185-198. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33884/basisupb.v7i1.1899>
- Sari, D. N., & Jumanto, J. (2015). A Contrastive Analysis between English Idioms and Their Indonesian Translations in the Novel *The Girl on the Train* by Paula Hawkins (2015). *E-Structural*, 1, (1), 88-100. <https://publikasi.dinus.ac.id/index.php/estructural/article/view/1824>
- Siregar, R. (2016). Pentingnya Pengetahuan Ideologi Penerjemahan Bagi Penerjemah [The Importance of Knowledge on Translation Ideologies for Translators]. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan Bahasa Dan Sastra*, 1, (1), 1-8. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/289234-pentingnya-pengetahuan-ideologi-penerjem-74a3ae35.pdf>
- Suprpto, Tarjana, S., & Nababan. (2019). A Study on the Techniques and Methods of the Translation of the Political Text in the International Political News in Printed Media. *Proceeding of International Conference on Art, Language, and Culture*. Surakarta: Universitas Negeri Sebelas Maret. <https://jurnal.uns.ac.id/icalc/article/view/28324>
- Tommy, Andrian. (2014). Klasifikasi Ragam Penerjemahan Berdasarkan Metode Penerjemahan dalam Diagram V Peter Newmark: Kajian Teoretis Aplikatif [Classification of Translation Types Based on Translation Methods within Peter Newmark's V Diagram: An Applicative Theoretical Study]. *Prosiding Seminar Hasil Penelitian Semester Ganjil 2013/2014*, (1), 45-66. ISSN 2337-7976
- Venuti, L. (2004). *The Translation Studies Reader* (L. Venuti & M. Baker, Eds.). Great Britain: Taylor & Francis e-Library.
- Venuti, L. (2004). *The Translator's Invisibility* (S. Bassnett & Lefevere Andre, Eds.). Great Britain: Taylor & Francis e-Library.
- Wahyuni, L. M. S., & Pradhana, N. I. (2017). Penerjemahan Majas Hiperbola dalam Novel "Kazemachi No Hito" Karya Ibuki Yuki [The Translation of Hyperboles in the Novel "Kazemachi No Hito" by Ibuki Yuki]. *Jurnal Humanis, Fakultas Ilmu Budaya Unud*, 20, 1 Agustus 2017, 57-65. <https://scholar.google.co.id/citations?user=EPT82XcAAAAJ&hl=en>
- Yamananda, I. (2016). A Translation Analysis of Superlative Form of Hyperbolic Expressions in the Novel Entitled "The Adventure of Sherlock Holmes" by Sir Arthur Conan Doyle. *An Undergraduate's Thesis*. file:///C:/Users/ASUS/Downloads/COVER.pdf.